

THE ROLE OF PRESCHOOL IN A CHILD'S LIFE

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Abstract: the role of a preschool educational institution in the life of a child of preschool age is of great importance in the life of a child, in the development of a child's personality. It is the preschool age that is the main foundation and the construction of a life scenario for the rest of a person's life.

This article discusses the positive aspects of visiting a preschool institution and how a preschool institution helps in the development of a child's personality.

Key words: child psychology, preschool age, socialization of the child, independence of the child, personality development, pedagogy of the preschool institution.

Preschool children are very active and inquisitive. They want to know as much as possible. They study, observe and try. Undoubtedly, family relationships play a huge role in the development of the child as a person, but the environment and social adaptation are also important.

Parents try to give their child all the best, but social adaptation and interaction with the world around them. Parents cannot give as well as it will be in an educational organization. The child himself needs to communicate with peers and is drawn to them.

Social adaptation is vital so that the child can easily enter the group of peers and communicate with them. Some parents believe that if a mother is free from work, or more simply a housewife, and there are also grandparents who devote a lot of attention, love and games to the child, then there is no urgent need to send the child to kindergarten, as the child is played, taken care of and has everything for development, but no matter how active and interesting communication with adults is, it will never replace communication with peers, since it is with peers that this is the most important experience of building relationships in society.

At preschool age, the child develops both physical and mental development, which are closely interconnected. At preschool age, the child's psyche strives for independence and inclusion in adult life, we very often hear the first phrases in a child at preschool age "I myself (a)", because the child tries to learn everything and try it out on his own experience.

Just as important is the fact that parents try to give everything to the child, they take care of the child, pamper, fulfill all the personal desires of the child, indulge all the whims of the child and the child, looking at this, thinks that everything revolves around him. He is the Universe and everything, and everyone owes him, the child does not appreciate the gifts received, but considers it for granted, and this indicates that the child develops childish egocentrism.

Egocentrism among preschoolers is a fairly common phenomenon, since the child is not aware of the existence of other people's points of view. Almost all parents are faced with the manifestation of children's egocentrism and it is very important to stop its development in time, until the greatness of one's own "I" has led to interpersonal conflicts.

Children's egocentric thinking usually manifests itself in the fact that the child is not able to accept the fact that others see the world around them in their own way. This happens because the child is focused only on himself, on his own thinking, positions and goals, his aspirations, experiences, sensations, and he does not quite understand that other positions, goals, experiences are possible. A person who has developed egocentrism does not adapt well in a team, society, he has conflict situations or he is too closed in himself and is completely unable to work in a team.

Therefore, a kindergarten where many kids go and everyone has their own personal opinion, desires, their own view of the world, their own scenarios of behavior give a very good idea that there is someone else's opinion, that others think differently. In kindergarten there is a teacher who will explain that you need to take into account other opinions, feelings, goals.

But I want to note that parents, in turn, should help the child understand that he is not the only one whose opinion, desires and views are correct. To get rid of the child's egocentrism is a big job for parents for his happy future and mutual understanding with others, and the kindergarten helps parents a lot in this. Let's touch on another important part of the benefits of attending a kindergarten for a child - in kindergarten, a child learns independence and acquires new skills.

If at home parents do a lot for the child in order to improve conditions, prevent falls and speed up the process of dressing, eating and much more, then in kindergarten the teacher will teach the child to do everything on his own, namely to change clothes, clean up toys, clean up after himself eat dishes, hold a spoon, go to the toilet on your own, wash your hands, clean up your pencils, paints, brushes, etc.

The independence of the child gives a clear understanding that if he can provide for his physiological and psychological needs on his own, he will grow up as a self-confident person. Independence develops a desire to act, further in spite of mistakes and failures, and also forms the character of the child.

And it is not unimportant to note that in kindergartens there is a day regimen strictly by the clock, which is very important for the healthy development of the child. The correct daily routine helps the child develop organization, academic performance, and contributes to the learning process.

The daily routine helps to control the balance of work and rest, avoid overload, alternate periods of physical and mental activity. Parents can also create the correct daily routine, but force majeure happens, which means a broken daily routine that needs to be restored again, which does not favorably affect the development of the child's body.

As the famous American psychologist and psychiatrist Eric Lennard Berne, known as the developer of transactional analysis and scenario analysis, said, people most often lay down the scenario of their entire life in childhood up to 6-8 years old, and then simply follow it, guided by what is so familiar, more convenient, safer.

Based on this, one can understand the importance of preschool education and upbringing, create conditions for the child to understand the world around him and his place in this world, develop the emotional and volitional spheres, master cultural and hygienic skills, daily routine, rules for handling toys, books, rules for relationships with other children and much more. The attitude of an adult to a child largely determines the formation of his personality, and parents should help him in this.

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